

ADVERSITY QUOTIENT®, PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND ROLES OF THE SCHOOL HEADS IN BUILDING THE LEVEL OF POSITIVE TEACHER'S IDENTITY

MITZHE GAE P. MAMINO¹

ELSA C. CALLO, ED. D²

17-S-EDD-03@lspu.edu.ph¹

elsa.callo@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0001-6074-3699¹

0000-0003-0785-4730²

Don Enrique Bautista Elementary School¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

Teachers confront various adversities-workload, pressure, and stress which add to the anxiety and challenges they experience. These and all life's adversities can affect their identity. Another essential concern is improving teachers' professional development, which directly impacts the teaching and learning process. School heads have a significant contribution and responsibility to develop a positive teacher's identity and ensure that teachers fulfill their duties and responsibilities to the best of their ability. This study aimed to ascertain the significant interrelationships between Adversity Quotient®, professional development, and roles of the principals in building the level of positive teacher's identity. This descriptive-correlational type of research utilized sets of questionnaires among 705 public elementary teachers in the Division of San Pablo City. Data were analyzed using frequency, percent, mean, standard deviation, Spearman's rank of correlation coefficient, and Multiple Regression. The hypotheses were tested at $p < .05$ level. Findings showed that the Adversity Quotient® of the teacher respondents was found not to be significantly related to the teacher's identity. However, there is a single or combination of two variables from professional development and the roles of school heads that directly affect teachers' identity. The researcher assumes that the teacher's identity is built when the teacher's professional development is carried out correctly. Moreover, the role of the school head being performed can affect how teachers develop their identity. The study suggested that school heads may be mindful of how to support and improve practices in areas that positively impact the formation of teaching identities to ensure positive educational outcomes.

Keywords: Adversity Quotient; professional development; roles of school head; teacher's identity; positive identity